

THE SOCIAL SIGNIFICANCE OF CINEMA

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Annotation. The article analyzes the social functions of national cinema and the causes and consequences of changes in the field of art.

Keywords: National cinema, social mission, modern society cinema, art, culture, spirituality, fiction, plot, hero, scenario.

In each type of cinema, genres have their own characteristics. The poetics of cinema, on the other hand, define the nature of genres, the ways in which they are used. For example, let's compare the portrait genre in painting and documentary cinema. Both arts tell the story of a person in this genre. In both unisi and this, the authors strive to show the uniqueness, uniqueness of this person. But in this, both the artist and the cinematographer use different means of expression. The artist uses composition, Colorite for his work, focuses attention on the hero's clothing, its details, and in particular meticulously describes the hero's face, the purpose of which is to vividly reveal his personality. In cinema, all this can be accompanied by the hero's plastic and, of course, speech, revealing the inner world of the image with special force. The movement in space and time Zero is cinematic and is important in the portrait genre. The genre in the cinema is not a hardened thing. They develop and regenerate, with some remaining in the past. The laws of the genre consist of artistic methods, a set of rules. They are needed for a stream a genre, because the film develops the genre and enriches it with new legacies. The director may sometimes deviate from the laws of the genre in pursuit of expressive brilliance in the implementation of his intention. In many cases, this is due to the film's chosen material, rather than the personality, originality of the director.

Directed By E.Ryazanov does not set himself the special task of updating the genre in each of his films, but implies a deviation from the law and rule of plots. That is why his famous Film "Carnival Night" is at the same time a lyrical, Ham comic comedy. "The silent romance "is a melodrama with elements of satire and tragedy, while" the sky of Dreams " is a vividly articulated drama. But the director broke the boundaries and incorporated neither comedy nor tragicomedy tones into them. The intermingling of genres is the internal rearrangement of their means of expression and principles in relation to the tasks that arise when creating a film. The mixed use of genres in contemporary cinema is a typical event. The mixed arrival of genres when dramaturgy, idea, direction are serious gives positive results. For Example, M. In the film "cranes

are flying" by Kalatozov, the melodramatic plot enters into a mutual relationship in a visual cohesive unit, approaching tragedy.

Therefore, the tools of an incredibly diverse genre with a plastic solution give the film a deep, rich meaning. The precise choice of genre when playwriting is ripe enough, the use of specific expressive means can determine the film's relevance. In feature films of the second half of the 20th century, the following genres can be distinguished: tragedy (L. Fayziev's "Star Of Glory", G.Kozinsev's "King Lear", D.Cameron's "Titanic" films), drama (SH.Abbosov's "you are not an orphan", E.Ishmuhammedov's book "Alvido, Gaur my youth...", B.Fleming's "my feelings flying in the winds"), comedy (Y. Protazanov's "Nasriddin Bukharoda", N.Ganiev's "The Adventures of Nasriddin", M.Abzalov's films "bride uprising", "Chimildiq"), melodrama (Bombay school films in India), as well as detective, adventures, fiction, etc. In almost every genre, different types of them are found. Comedy is a distinct genre with distinct characters, it is a musical (Y.A'zamov's "Maftuningman"), domestic (directed by Sh.Abbosov's "Mahalla duv-duv gap"), hajviy (E.Ryazanov's "garage"). Situation comedies also exist (Chaplin's first films). In the early - early days of cinema, "pyroxen" comedies were popular, in which, of course, the characters would throw stones at each other. In documentary and non-documentary cinema, the genres of portraiture, ocherk, Scenic film, filminterview have become popular. Animated cinema, on the other hand, embodied the entire wealth of existing genres. In artistic creation, it is important which genre the upcoming film should belong to, since it also determines the style and way of action of the actor in role-playing. The accuracy of which genre the Film belongs to effectively affects its good perception by the viewer.

Cinema educates a person. Gives him spiritual nourishment. It is necessary to learn from him to relax, strive for the Ozu, appreciate great feelings. But the goal of private films is to make a good income from cinema. But when the money that went to some shallow films was spent on making films that encouraged national feelings of pride and pride, or thought about the anxiety, spirituality of the common man of today, cinema was felt to keep pace with the era. Cinema is becoming an integral part of spiritual life. Therefore, it was entrusted with important responsibilities. It is necessary to try to expand the range of topics using new-new opportunities in order to mature the national spirit in the hearts of people, raise their culture and spirituality, and seriously pay attention to the cultivation of their spiritual and mental progress. Cinema has a strong influence on the hearts and minds of young people. Naturally, it attracts the attention of

sociologists, aestheticians, art historians, cultural theorists [6]. Now is the time to make truly national films that tell about our history, illuminate today's process of national revival and renewal, and direct us to a bright future.

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